

Britain Coal in the 19th and 20th Centuries : The Black Gold in industrialization and global history

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Introduction

This Article is about the Britain's Coal in the 19th and 20th Centuries: The Black Gold of Industrialization and Global History . The history of Britain's coal industry in 19th and 20th centuries cannot be understood in isolation. It must be placed within the broader framework of global industrial development, imperial energy demands, and the shifting geopolitical economy of fossil fuels. This essay asks: How did global developments in energy use, technology, and economic restructuring affect the trajectory of the British coal industry and its global impacts especially during and after nationalisation in 1946? And how did Britain's national strategies for managing decline—through technological investment, restructuring, and labor reform—compare with or diverge from international trends? Yet, despite these ambitions, British coal experienced continued decline in the second half of the century. From sharp employment cuts and pit closures to growing regional disparities and deindustrialisation, Britain mirrored broader patterns in the Global North, where once-central extractive industries were increasingly marginalised in the age of oil, automation, and climate consciousness. In examining Britain's coal sector in global context, this Article argues that nationalisation temporarily postponed, but could not reverse, the global forces driving coal's decline. the Article situates the connection of the global history and the British coal industry within a transnational history of energy and industrial transformation . article draws on 14 sources, including 9 academic books and journal articles, and 5 reputable online sources. This combination ensures both historical depth and up-to-date perspectives on the British coal industry.

The British Coal Industry in the Nineteenth Century: Industrial Foundations and Expansion within Global Trade Networks

The British coal industry came during the nineteenth century to be regarded as one of the three or four staple industries of the country.¹

In the mid-1850s the UK had an intensive coal industry. Coal was used to produce steam power for the majority of British industries. The source of coal was from exposed coalfields, located mainly in the midland valley of Scotland, the north and South Wales coalfields, and from the major coalfields of England, located in Northumberland & Durham, Yorkshire / Nottinghamshire / Derbyshire, and Lancashire. They were all true bituminous coals, from the Carboniferous Coal Measures. In addition, anthracite was produced from the western side of the south Wales coalfield. East of the English border with Wales the Coal Measures strata are generally overlain by the Permo-Triassic unconformity. In some areas, particularly in the English Midlands, scattered coalfields occur as inliers, brought to the surface by folding and faulting. Major examples include those of Shropshire, Staffordshire, and Leicestershire. As the coalfields expanded, it was realised that there was the potential for concealed coalfields to exist beneath the Permo-Triassic strata, and occasional exploratory boreholes were put down to prove coal. They met with little success, and those who did encounter coal were disappointing as the drilling technology at the time was inadequate to prove the thickness of the coal seams with any degree of accuracy. The friability of coal resulted in just a few fragments of coal being

¹ B. R. Mitchell, *Economic Development of the British Coal Industry 1800–1914* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1984), 1.

recovered in the drill samples, and any coal horizons were generally recorded as being too thin to mine .²

Down to the third quarter of the nineteenth century the export trade had only been of limited importance to the coal industry and the share of coal in the value of Britain's total exports had been negligible. As late as 1860 exports, including bunker-coal, represented little more than one-tenth of Britain's coal output and little more than one-fortieth of the value of her total exports. ² From this point, however, advance was not only continuous and rapid, but the tendency to accelerated growth observable in the industry at large was here most marked. In 1869 British coal exports amounted to 13 million tons; by 1887 this figure had risen to 31·7 millions; and twenty-six years later in 1913 exports, including bunkers, amounted to 98·3 million tons and accounted for more than one-third of the annual output of coal. By this time coal was responsible for more than one-tenth in value of Britain's export trade. The greater part of these shipments went to continental Europe. In 1875 Britain's best customers had been France and Germany each taking more than two million tons of coal annually-and, following them, Italy, the Scandinavian countries, Russia and Spain, each consuming upwards of half a million tons.¹ Outside Europe demand was smaller but there were important growth points in Egypt-largely for bunkering purposes-the British East Indies, the Caribbean and Latin America.³ Unfortunately, by the end of the 1980s the use of coal was in decline. Collieries were closed and what was left of the industry was privatised and all exploration work ceased. The author's 'Memories of Coal' are very personal as he was employed as a geologist in the UK coal

² R. W. Vernon, "An Island of Coal: The British National Coal Board and Their 'Plans for Coal' 1947 to 1987," *Comunicações Geológicas* (March 2024), © 2023 LNEG – Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia IP, 88. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/614520811.pdf>.

³ Taylor, A. J.. "CHAPTER 2. THE COAL INDUSTRY" In *The Development of British Industry and Foreign Competition 1875–1914* edited by Derek H. Aldcroft, 37-70. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 1968, 39 . <https://doi.org/10.3138/9781487571900-003>

industry for 24 years (1969 to 1993) and was very much involved with the second 'Plan for Coal' and was peripheral to 'Plan2000', as a dedicated exploration unit implemented the latter.

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Decline and Adaptation: British Coal Industry's Challenges and Labor Shifts during the Early 20th Century and World War II

The major change was the collapse of exports which fell from 83.3 million tons to 48.7 million tons in 1938.⁵ At the start of World War I annual coal production in the UK was less than 300 million tons per annum produced by about 3,000 collieries. Some were private mines, employing just a few men, but by this time, the majority were public-financed colliery companies that often worked a number of collieries in their group. In addition to coal production, they might also produce gas, coke for the metallurgical industry, and chemicals. In this period, very little geological exploration was being conducted and recording of the underground geology was the responsibility of the colliery survey department. Surface boreholes were often logged by someone employed by the drilling company, often from a university geology department, or a mine surveyor who had overall geological knowledge of a particular coalfield. It is no wonder that sometimes coal seams were occasionally miscorrelated! In later years staff of the British Geological Survey would be involved in borehole logging. The 1920s and 1930s saw periods of depression and social unrest that resulted in industrial disputes. The coal industry was in decline, and several proposals to nationalise the coal industry were mooted. However, they were shelved at the start of World War II. During World War II it was apparent that there was a shortfall in coal miners, who were leaving the industry to serve in the Armed Forces, so a scheme was introduced to conscript

⁴ Vernon, "An Island of Coal," 88.

⁵ Walter Minchinton, "The Rise and Fall of the British Coal Industry: A Review Article," *VSWG: Vierteljahrschrift für Sozial- und Wirtschaftsgeschichte* 77, no. 2 (1990): 219. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/20735640>.

young men into the coal mining industry. Known as 'Bevin Boys', named after the then Minister of Labour and National Service, Ernest Bevin, the scheme was initiated in December 1943 . [When the author joined the industry in 1969, he noted that many of the original 'Bevin Boys' who had stayed in the industry, had risen to managerial positions.] By the end of World War II annual coal output had fallen further. ⁶

Britain's Coal Industry: Navigating Global Trade, Fragmented Growth, and Technological Innovation from the Industrial Revolution to Late 20th Century Decline

Britain's dominance of the world's export trade in coal had its basis in the facts of commercial geography. Although the cost of mining coal was increasing more rapidly in Britain in the quartercentury before 1914 than in Germany or the United States-or indeed than in any other country-British coalowners were able to maintain their firm grip on European and South American markets because of the enormous advantage which easy sea communication gave to the coal of South Wales and North-east England. This blessing conferred upon Britain's coal industry by a seemingly beneficent providence had been reinforced by the skill of her inventors and ship builders. Over the half-century before 1914 the development of the steamship had produced a substantial decrease in freighting charges. Rates from Cardiff to Bordeaux, Lisbon, Genoa and Kronstadt had been more than halved, while to more distant ports, among them Port Said, Singapore and Buenos Aires the reduction was even greater.⁷ A characteristic of coal mining in Britain for centuries was the fact that the industry consisted of a large number of small mines. This made it more like agriculture than industry. This and the dispersed nature of working makes it difficult to talk of a coal industry before 1830. growth in output was largely by the opening of new mines, mostly by new concerns. As late as 1880 there were over 3330

⁶ Vernon, "An Island of Coal," 89.

⁷ Taylor, "The Coal Industry," 41.

mines in the industry. Although some consolidation then took place, in 1913 there were still 2700 mines including 800 small producers employing less than 50 men. Some concentration had taken place by 1938 when there were a number of large colliery firms but, Supple notes, throughout its history in the private sector the industry remained highly fragmented.⁸ Coal has been a major industry in the United Kingdom since the start of the industrial revolution in the 18th century, with production estimates in 1750 at five million metric tons. In 1913, UK coal production peaked at 292 million metric tons.⁹

At the start of the 20th century almost 100% of Britain's electricity was generated by coal plants. By 1950, its dominance remained largely unchallenged at 96%, and in the late 1960s and 1970s Britain's state-owned Central Electricity Generating Board ushered in a new generation of super coal plants. In 1966, Ferrybridge C began generating electricity on the River Aire in West Yorkshire. It opened with a generating capacity of 2,000 megawatts from four 500MW units, the first in Europe to create electricity from a generating unit of this size. Within two years, coal plants of a similar size mushroomed up across Britain's coalfields: Ratcliffe-on-Soar, Cottam and West Burton A all began generating power in Nottinghamshire; and the Eggborough power plant started operations in North Yorkshire. By the end of the decade, the Ironbridge and Rugeley coal power plants began generating power in the West Midlands. In total, about 12 power stations of this scale began generating electricity in the years between 1966 and 1974, culminating in the giant Drax plant in North Yorkshire. After a sharp slump during the 1984-1985 miners' strike coal power failed to return to the highs recorded at

⁸ Minchinton, "The Rise and Fall of the British Coal Industry," 221 .

⁹ M. Garside, "Coal Production in the United Kingdom (UK) 1913–2023," *Statista*, published September 17, 2024, <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1125925/historic-coal-production-in-the-united-kingdom/>.

the start of the decade. By the 1990s, Britain's dash for gas power and rising environmental concerns spelled the beginning of a long existential decline for coal.¹⁰

The Steam Engine, Coal Nationalisation, and Social Transformations in Britain's Mid-20th Century Industrial Landscape

The greatest invention of the Industrial Revolution was the steam engine, which transformed all manner of tasks and transportation from relying on human, animal, wind, or water power to using the far greater, cheaper, and more consistent power of machines. The steam engine was invented in the first place so that coal mines could be mined deeper and floodwaters pumped out of the shafts. ¹¹ Coal was a major source of male employment in Britain in 1947, when the industry was nationalised by Clement Attlee's Labour government. 8 Table 1 shows the broad pattern, with a significant drop in overall industry employment in the decade or so from 1957, a slower decline in the late 1960s and 1970s, and then a precipitous drop after 1984–1985. This employment was concentrated geographically in the coalfields of central Scotland, northern England and the Midlands, and south Wales, with small outcrops elsewhere, notably Kent. In Scotland one-third of the mining workforce at the time of nationalisation was deployed in Fife, where roughly one in four men worked in the coal industry in 1951 and one in ten in 1971. The gender effects of the acceleration of deindustrialisation after the strike were complex. The share of female employment became more important as 250,000

¹⁰ Jillian Ambrose, "The Deep History of British Coal: From the Romans to the Ratcliffe Shutdown," *The Guardian*, September 30, 2024, <https://www.theguardian.com/business/2024/sep/30/the-deep-history-of-british-coal-from-the-romans-to-the-ratcliffe-shutdown>.

¹¹ Mark Cartwright, "Coal Mining in the British Industrial Revolution," *World History Encyclopedia*, published March 17, 2023, <https://www.worldhistory.org/article/2201/coal-mining-in-the-british-industrial-revolution/>.

or so male jobs in coal were eradicated across England, Scotland and Wales. Women were compelled to carry this greater burden with lower paid service sector wages because many engineering jobs were also eliminated. More positively, in a number of coalfield territories women as well as men built on local traditions of trade union organisation to secure better service sector pay and conditions in supermarkets and care homes than those which applied elsewhere.¹² A large number of British coal industries in separate districts, more or less loosely connected. The connections became stronger as the years passed, but the diversity of physical conditions and of local customs has ensured that. Even today, despite much uniformity introduced through mechanisation, and after well over thirty years of national ownership, the industry is by no means homogeneous. Not least of the many differences between the coalfields are those in the markets which they serve. In the nineteenth century these differences were so pronounced that it often conceals more than it illuminates to discuss them solely in terms of a national demand for coal.¹³ At the beginning of the twentieth century Britain remained the largest producer of coal in Europe, with an annual output of 229 million tons. As its neighbors industrialized, their coal production rose rapidly. The German lands, which had extracted just 6 million tons of coal in 1850, produced 43 million tons in 1871, the year of German unification. In 1900 Germany produced 150 million tons, followed by France (33 million tons) and Belgium (24 million tons). Although British fears of industrial decline—or at least loss of predominance in coal—focused on Germany, the greatest challenge came from across the Atlantic. The United States, which had mined just 8 million tons of coal in 1850, produced 245 million tons in 1900, making it the world's leading coal country. The adoption of coal-burning steam engines not only made it possible for factories to increase production; it also freed them from the geographical and seasonal constraints inherent in the use of water power. Instead of

¹² Jim Phillips, "The Meanings of Coal Community in Britain since 1947," *Contemporary British History* 32, no. 1 (2018): [42-44].

¹³ Phillips, "The Meanings of Coal Community," 10.

remaining dispersed across the countryside, factories became concentrated near coal mines and coal transportation routes, creating urban centers where workers and consumers lived. ¹⁴

Trade Challenges and Production Dynamics in Britain's Coal Industry: Export Decline, Market Stabilization, and Economic Analysis (1920–1945)

The facts relating to Great Britain as a whole and to the Con-tinent provide a strong argument in favour of an international price agreement, and such an agreement is now within the region of practical politics. It is clear that difficulties would be encountered in attempting to reach an agreement. The re-direction of trade since the war would be regarded as permanent by those who have benefited and as temporary by those who have suffered, and this conflict of view would lead to difficulties in determining the precise scope of an agreement. Again, the recent re-direction of trade within Great Britain has increased the difficulty of establishing an agreement which would be satisfactory to all the districts. The policy of the Government in enforcing the formation of district committees for the regulation of prices and output seems to me not merely desirable but, in view of what has already been stated, inevitable. But the fixing of district quotas and prices is almost . It will be observed that British exports of coal have fallen since 1913 by over 20,000,000 tons, but that since 1925 there has been little change. The bunker trade has fallen by over 4,000,000 tons, but again it may be said that since 1925 the trade has been comparatively stable. We find, therefore, that there has been a fall of over 26,000,000 tons in the total quantity of coal which is shipped abroad, and that (allowing for the 1920 stoppage) such trade has been remarkably stable since 1925. The fluctuations that have taken place in total production since 1925 are wholly explained by fluctuations in the amount

¹⁴ Peter Thorsheim, *Inventing Pollution: Coal, Smoke and Culture in Britain since 1800* (Athens: Ohio University Press, 2006), 14.

of coal available for home consumption. But before we pass on to examine home trade I venture to submit one further comment upon the statistics of exports. It will be agreed that the export figures for 1923 and 1924 were so largely influenced by the dislocation of the German industry that they are practically useless for comparative purposes.¹⁵ Between 1920 and 1926 the coal-mining industry of this country and of continental countries was subjected to a series of abnormal and temporary influences; it received sharp blows which prevented the inherent non-human forces from producing those results which they would otherwise have done. The British industry suffered from stoppages in 1920 and 1921; in 1923-24 it experienced a boom which was due not to a general recovery of trade but to the dislocation of the German industry during the French occupation of the Ruhr. The coal subsidy which followed the restoration of the gold standard, and represented an attempt to escape the immediate consequences of that measure, introduced an artificial element, and after this was removed the most severe struggle in the history of the coal trade took place.¹⁶ Demand for coal was at its peak during the early decades of the 20th century. Gradually demand fell for coal and the mines in the region closed one by one, especially after Nationalisation in 1947. The narrow seams, coupled with mine gas problems made production expensive, and many smaller pits were closed. The larger pits survived into the 1960s when reduced national demand together with competition from more economical coalfields led to the closure of the last remaining pit in 1973.¹⁷ A production function can be determined by applying multi-variate analysis to spatial data or to time-series. For coal-getting in Great Britain both methods can be used, the time series relating to the country as a whole and the spatial data to the twenty-five coal districts. It is not possible to carry out analyses of time-series for individual districts, since data of coal got by pneumatic

¹⁵ J. H. Jones, "The Present Position of the British Coal Trade," *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society* 93, no. 1 (1930): [14, 26-27].

¹⁶ Jones, "The Present Position of the British Coal Trade," 21.

¹⁷ British Geological Survey, "Coal Mining History," *Foundations of the Mendips*, British Geological Survey (NERC).

picks in the different coal regions have not been published for a sufficiently long time. The spatial analysis is carried out for the year 1945, the latest for which such information is available, while the time series are limited to the period 1927 to 1943 by the difficulty in estimating the capital equipment in use before 1927 and the change in definition of manshiffs worked at the coal-face after 1943. In the analysis of time-series it is necessary to include a residual time trend to take account of changes in productivity over time, not associated with the inputs measured in the manner indicated. The definition of capital implies that this residual trend is primarily connected with changes in skill, intensity of effort on the part of labour, and the state of the seams being worked, rather than with technical progress. The time series, on the other hand, relating to Great Britain as a whole tend to suggest, as anticipated, that there may be slightly increasing true returns to scale in coal-mining, although we cannot estimate the "population" value with very much precision. Secondly, the results of the time analysis are averages over the period, and as capitalization proceeded apace between 1927 and 1943, the value for capital at the beginning of the period was presumably appreciably greater than at the end. It would, then, be reasonable to expect the marginal product of capital in 1945 to be less than the average for 1927 to 1943 .¹⁸

From Nationalisation to Decline: The Transformation of the British Coal Industry, 1946–1990

The Coal Industry Nationalisation Act 1946 resulted in the complete nationalisation of the coal industry (Coal Industry Nationalisation Act, 1946). On 12th July 1946 the National Coal Board (NCB), came into being. On the vesting date, 1 January 1947, the productive assets of some 970 or more private collieries and their employees were transferred to the NCB. As part of the nationalisation process, there were also a number of establishments set up to future-proof the

¹⁸K. S. Lomax, "Coal Production Functions for Great Britain," *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series A (General)* 113, no. 3 (1950): 346-351

industry and ensure it was kept up to date with advances in mining technology. Important examples include: i) The Mining Research Establishment in West London was formed in 1951. It merged with another, the Central Engineering Establishment to form the Mining Research and Development Establishment (MRDE - Bretby) in 1969. This organisation looked at advances in mining machinery and studied in detail the effects of such machinery on the mining environment. ii) Coal Research Establishment (CRE – Stoke Orchard) was opened in 1950. The CRE's main objective was to improve the efficiency of burning coal, whilst also trying to keep emissions down. It was instrumental in the production of a range of smokeless fuels for the domestic market. The scientific functions of the industry were also brought under one unit, and they would be responsible for scientific analysis of the industry. One of their functions was to administer the coal survey. The responsibility of the survey was to map the depth, thickness and structure of individual coal seams as well as mapping chemical and physical properties. The survey was also important for establishing a system of seam correlation using marine bands, tonsteins, and plant spore assemblages in coal. Standardisation was perhaps one of the main achievements of nationalisation, as well as a proper career structure for employees. For example, an apprenticeship scheme was introduced for the various trades (surveying, electrical, mechanical, and mining, etc.), and common safety standards were applied to all branches of the industry.¹⁹ The 1970s and 1980s marked a crucial phase in the history of the British coal industry. The period may be characterised as a false dawn that spawned hopes and illusions about a bright future for the industry that were soon to be disappointed. Yet heightened expectations took on a life of their own, and arguably played no small role in accelerating the long-term trajectory of decline and in defining its conflictual nature. The 1970s followed upon years of contraction which the preeminent authority on the topic, writing in the early 1980s, has called "the most difficult time ever known in the coal industry" . Between 1958 and 1973,

¹⁹ Vernon, "An Island of Coal," 89.

coal's share in total UK energy consumption fell from 80 percent to 37 percent. Of the six traditional markets for coal—domestic, gas, private industry, railways, steel and electricity—the industry lost the first four and came under severe pressure in the field of electricity generation by the switch to oil-burn in power stations and the nuclear power programme. The scale of the rundown of coal in the decade preceding the 1970s was indeed remarkable: Between 1957 and 1970/1, manpower was cut from 700,000 employees to 287,000, while the number of producing collieries fell from 822 to 292. Meanwhile, total output was reduced by one third, from 227 million tons in 1957 to 145 million tons in 1970/1. Yet, contraction went hand in hand with considerable gains in productivity, due to the wide introduction of mechanised methods of coal getting.²⁰ This admirable development in the power of the world's industrial system to provide a larger amount of goods and services with the same or a less consumption of coal was not always to the disadvantage of the coal industry. Its general effect was, presumably, to stimulate the total demand for industrial energy, so the coal industry gained benefits, even while it was losing ground. But the adverse effects were sharply felt in a world where the coal industries had, until the first World War, been expanding rapidly and were themselves growing more efficient in turning out more coal for each man employed and for every shift worked. Already, before 1914, the growth of the coal industry in Europe had been arrested. Output on the continent increased between 1913 and 1929, but only by approximately the amount representing the fall in British production. In the United States, the coal industry did not grow at all over these same years, judged by the amount of coal won. This lack of development created fierce competition between field and field in the United States, with serious consequences for the American miner's wages. In Europe, where no common political institutions existed and where three big coal exporting countries were to be found in Great

²⁰ Jörg Arnold, "The Death of Sympathy: Coal Mining, Workplace Hazards, and the Politics of Risk in Britain, ca. 1970–1990," *Historical Social Research / Historische Sozialforschung* 41, no. 3 (2016): 93.

Britain, Germany and Poland, the fight was not only between field and field but also between sovereign state and another. This was especially clear after tyag, when the onset of the world industrial depression aggravated the situation beyond measure. The light was the fiercer because from tgray onwards a remarkable change had been coming over the technique of deep coal mining, and the continent had been one of the main centres of innovation, The immediate effect of technical progress was to increase substantially I the productivity of the mines, although the bulk and in some countries the whole of the increase in output per manshift due to this cause was obtained after 1929 . Potential over-capacity was no new thing in the coal industries, where pis do not easily go out of busince and whitre the expensive apparatus of modern deep-mining makes it important to continue production so long as there is a hope of rarming anything towards overheads. This had been observed in the United States as early as 1900 and noted in Great Britain early in the twenties.²¹ Of course, there had to be a plan for the nationalised coal industry, and the first ‘Plan for Coal’ was published in November 1950, although some aspects of it were already being implemented . It was proposed to spend £635 million to reconstruct the industry. By the 1960s, production would be 240 million tons of coal per annum. It was proposed to close about 450 collieries thereby reducing the workforce by 80,000 miners to 618,000 by 1965. The loss in capacity would be replaced by sinking new collieries and increase the efficiency of existing mines. Opencast (strip) mining introduced during World War II would be phased out by 1965. In 1959 the plan was revised, and the output target was raised by a further 10 million tons of coal . It was inevitable that the majority of the new collieries to be sunk into concealed reserves would pass through a significant thickness of water-bearing strata (sandstones and limestones) in the Permo-Triassic. There was some experience in doing this. In the Kent coalfield, for example, many of the shafts were sunk using large diameter augers,

²¹ W. H. B. Court, “Problems of the British Coal Industry between the Wars,” *The Economic History Review* 15, no. 1/2 (1945), 12.

and iron tubing (a steel lining tube). Elsewhere, later shaft sinking would employ freezing techniques. The first attempts were problematic. At Thorne colliery in the Yorkshire coalfield, which at the start of the 20th century would be one of the deepest collieries in the UK, shaft sinking started in 1912 and finished in 1925. It was sunk through 460 m of PermoTriassic strata. However, water in the Thorne colliery shafts was always a problem. By the 1950s however, the freezing technique had been perfected, and the shafts for many of the new collieries, like Kellingley in Yorkshire, would be sunk successfully.²² In the early 1970s, the coal industry was in slow decline because the emphasis of UK power requirements was trending towards oil and gas. 'The dash for gas' as it became known meant that reliance was being placed more on imported oil and gas for energy needs. Power stations were switching to gas. In addition, there were also nuclear power stations that supplied a relatively small percentage of total energy requirements. Then in 1973, the Yom Kippur War occurred in the Middle East. It was a major conflict between Arabic and Israeli nations, and it disrupted oil and gas supply to the UK and elsewhere. It had the effect of highlighting just how vulnerable the UK's energy needs were. Consequently, the whole of the UK's energy policy was re-examined, and the decision was made to increase coal production and maintain it at a certain level. The second 'Plan for Coal' was published in 1974 . In essence, the plan required an extra 40 to 42 million tons of coal to be produced per annum required by 1985. On top of normal coal production, the additional coal would come from: i) An extra 9 million tons of coal by extending the life of existing collieries. ii) An extra 13 million tons from major schemes. This would entail opening up areas of new reserves, and often accessing them with surface conveyor tunnels (Drifts), to speed up the process of bringing coal to the surface. iii) An extra 15 million tons by increasing opencast production. iv) A further 20 million tons would be required from new collieries. Once again,

²² Vernon, "An Island of Coal," 89.

geological exploration would concentrate on the concealed parts of known coalfields, in four areas: Yorkshire, Nottinghamshire, West and South Midlands. In Yorkshire, one borehole had been drilled just to the south of the City of York and disproved the concept that the incrop of the concealed Coal Measures trended east-west beneath the Vale of York.²³

Conclusion

This essay explores the history of coal in Britain, focusing on how its development, nationalisation, and eventual decline were not only shaped by internal economic and political factors but also deeply influenced by global historical forces. By examining technological innovation, international energy markets, and comparative labour trends, the essay highlights how Britain's coal industry both impacted and was impacted by broader global transformations during the 20th century. The transformation of Britain's coal industry in the 20th century cannot be fully understood without placing it within the broader framework of global history. The nationalisation of the industry in 1947 reflected a domestic effort to modernise production and improve labour conditions. However, these efforts were soon challenged by global shifts in energy consumption, such as the rise of oil and nuclear power, and increasing international competition. The decline of coal was not simply a British phenomenon—it was part of a worldwide restructuring of industrial energy systems and labour markets. In this way, the story of Britain's coal industry reflects not only national policy and economic change, but also the global currents of technological progress, labour transformation, and shifting energy demands. It serves as a case study of how local industries are shaped—and ultimately undone—by global forces.

²³ Vernon, "An Island of Coal," 90-91 .

Bibliography

1. Ambrose, Jillian. "The Deep History of British Coal: From the Romans to the Ratcliffe Shutdown." *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/business/2024/sep/30/the-deep-history-of-british-coal-from-the-romans-to-the-ratcliffe-shutdown>.
2. Arnold, Jörg. "The Death of Sympathy: Coal Mining, Workplace Hazards, and the Politics of Risk in Britain, ca. 1970–1990." *Historical Social Research / Historische Sozialforschung* 41, no. 3 (2016).
3. British Geological Survey. "Coal Mining History." *Foundations of the Mendips*. British Geological Survey (NERC).
4. Cartwright, Mark. "Coal Mining in the British Industrial Revolution." *World History Encyclopedia*. Published March 17, 2023. <https://www.worldhistory.org/article/2201/coal-mining-in-the-british-industrial-revolution/>.
5. Court, W. H. B. "Problems of the British Coal Industry between the Wars." *The Economic History Review* 15, no. 1/2 (1945): 1–24.
6. Garside, M. "Coal Production in the United Kingdom (UK) 1913–2023." *Statista*. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1125925/historic-coal-production-in-the-united-kingdom/>.
7. Jones, J. H. "The Present Position of the British Coal Trade." *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society* 93, no. 1 (1930).
8. Lomax, K. S. "Coal Production Functions for Great Britain." *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series A (General)* 113, no. 3 (1950): 346–351.
9. Minchinton, Walter. "The Rise and Fall of the British Coal Industry: A Review Article." *VSWG: Vierteljahrschrift für Sozial- und Wirtschaftsgeschichte* 77, no. 2 (1990). <http://www.jstor.org/stable/20735640>.
10. Mitchell, B. R. *Economic Development of the British Coal Industry 1800–1914*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1984.
11. Phillips, Jim. "The Meanings of Coal Community in Britain since 1947." *Contemporary British History* 32, no. 1 (2018).
12. Taylor, A. J. "The Coal Industry." In *The Development of British Industry and Foreign Competition 1875–1914*, edited by Derek H. Aldcroft, 37–70. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 1968.
13. Thorsheim, Peter. *Inventing Pollution: Coal, Smoke and Culture in Britain since 1800*. Athens: Ohio University Press, 2006.
14. Vernon, R. W. "An Island of Coal: The British National Coal Board and Their 'Plans for Coal' 1947 to 1987." *Comunicações Geológicas*, March 2024. 2023 LNEG – Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia IP